

PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS AS A TOOL OF PREPARATION FOR ORGANIZATIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This study reveals the technologies of the pedagogical process of preparation for organizational activities.

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Knowledge, skills and abilities are the basis of innovative methods of training specialists. Students receive knowledge as a result of the pedagogical process. All this graduates of educational institutions receive in the process of communicating with teachers or on their own, especially when it comes to "distance learning" or "virtual education".

This kind of education is now very widely used in modern education. This has become relevant due to the epidemiological situation in the world. First of all, we are talking about creating good, didactically perfect textbooks. Their content, structure and form must first of all take into account the isolation of the student from teachers and fellow students. At the same time, "the student should easily see the main thing in the course that he must certainly master, and that this main thing stands out in relief, possibly many times and in various ways."

Despite the rather large independence of students, this kind of training, which is often called "virtual", requires the presence of "highly qualified faculty of the department." This is connected not only with writing rather specific textbooks, but also with advising students and monitoring knowledge. The latter (in conditions of

distance learning) carries an extensive "heap" of problems. Therefore, "it is necessary to transform the education system in such a way that control ceases to be the driving force of the educational process and is replaced by students' interest in the search for knowledge."

And here we just come to the personality-developing education. According to the fair opinion of specialists, students receive education of two kinds:

firstly, they acquire knowledge, skills and abilities within the chosen specialty; secondly, they are given the opportunity to become a creative, independently thinking, comprehensively developed personality. And for this they should not just attend lectures or seminars.

It is important to communicate with a thinker, after listening to which you can set yourself in motion. We are talking about the personality of the teacher, communication with which allows you to modify the image of the world, enrich it with new elements.

The image of the world is an integral multi-level system of a person's ideas about the world, about other people, about himself and his activities. It is of great (key) importance from the standpoint of intrauniversity education and personal development.

It is the teacher who forms the students' conceptual vision of the world, ways of life in it in everyday acts of learning. He outlines areas of personal and professional growth, demonstrates images of constructive behavior, directs the development process towards correcting mistakes programmed by nature.

As the image of the world develops, it becomes more and more identical to the personality itself. As more and more holistic reality is reflected in the consciousness, it penetrates deeper and deeper into the sphere of the human psyche (feelings).

A developing personality, as it were, "looks" deeper into itself. Fear begins to play an increasingly important role in life, as a feeling of dependence or loss of something. And it is this fear that largely becomes the driving force of the

pedagogical process.

It can be about "the fear of the imperfection of this person" or the fear of the imperfection of our life. This kind of feeling forces one to take an increasingly active life position and, first of all, it concerns the pedagogical process, communication with the personality of the teacher (high school teacher).

This kind of fear can be called "fear of interest." It should be distinguished from the fear associated with the assessment of a student's knowledge (its value in the conditions of personality-developing education is smaller than in the traditional forms of teaching students at a university).

According to S.I. Gessen, the most important principles of personality-developing education are freedom and duty. The purpose of education, in his opinion, is not only to familiarize the student with the cultural, including scientific, achievements of mankind. Its goal is also (or simultaneously) the formation of a highly moral, free and responsible personality. And this "is acquired only through work on superpersonal tasks."

Freedom is the creation of the new, which has not existed in the world before. Duty is the unconditional fulfillment of one's duties (discipline is possible through freedom, and freedom through the law of duty). Both "nourish" fear, which (as already noted) is closely connected with the pedagogical process in a higher educational institution.

It is no coincidence that not all students fully support the idea of personality-developing education (or, in other words, "pedagogics of cooperation"). Among the students we surveyed, 67% of this kind of students. The remaining 33% believe that the main role in higher education should belong to the "pedagogy of requirements". In other words, not every university student can take on the "burden of freedom and duty." It is easier to obey the requirements of the teacher, (especially if they are also fair).

Bibliography

1. Закон Республики Узбекистан «О физической культуре и спорте» 4 сентября 2015 г. № ЗРУ-394
2. Закон Республики Узбекистан «О правах лиц с инвалидностью» 15 октября 2020 г. № ЗРУ-641
3. Закон Республики Узбекистан «О государственно-частном партнерстве» 10.05.2019 г. № ЗРУ-537
4. Государственный комитет Республики Узбекистан по статистике <https://gender.stat.uz/>
5. Указ президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию и популяризации физической культуры и спорта в Республике Узбекистан» от 24 января 2020 г.
7. Rashidov A. U, "Formation of Styles of Managerial Thinking as a Factor in the Preparation of a Future Specialist for Managerial Activities in the Field of Physical Culture and Sports." JournalNX, vol. 7, no. 03, 2021, pp. 172-176.
8. Rashidov A. U. The importance of studying the social portrait of a modern manager for the formation of a methodology for preparing future specialists for managerial activities in the field of physical culture and sports //Eurasian Journal of Sport Science. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 212-218.
9. Рашидов А. У. РАЗВИТИЕ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В СФЕРЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – Т. 27. – С. 66-70.